

TOURIST SPOTS' READINESS AND TOURISTS' REVISIT INTENTION : MEDIATING ROLE OF TOURISTS' SATISFACTION AND MODERATING ROLE OF TRANSPORTATION FACILITIES

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Abstract

This study explores the effect of tourist spots' readiness on tourists' revisit intention through the mediating effect of tourists' satisfaction and the moderating effect of transportation facilities. Using convenience sampling, data has been collected from 306 tourists from eight divisions of Bangladesh through a structured survey questionnaire. The partial least square-structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) has been used to assess the measurement and structural models of the study. The findings show no direct relationship between tourist spots' readiness and tourists' revisit intention in Bangladesh. However, a direct positive relationship is evident between tourist spots' readiness and tourists' satisfaction, and between tourists' satisfaction and revisit intention. Additionally, tourists' satisfaction mediates the relationship between tourist spots' readiness and tourists' revisit intention, and transportation facilities moderate the relationship between the tourists' satisfaction and revisit intention. These findings generate important theoretical and practical implications for academics, policymakers, and tourism practitioners.

Keywords : Bangladesh, Destination Image, LDC, Tourism Competitiveness, Tourists' Loyalty.

1. INTRODUCTION

Repeat visitors offer more revenue, recommend others, and contribute to branding and cost reduction (Park & Yoon, 2009). Consequently, determining tourists' revisit intentions recently received much attention from destination managers and tourism researchers (Pratminingsih, Rudatin, & Rimenta, 2014). The readiness of a tourist spot, particularly the destination's image, also received considerable attention in tourism marketing research (Pike, Pontes, & Kotsi, 2021). Therefore, understanding the relationship between tourist spots' readiness and tourists' revisit intention has become significant to destination competitiveness studies (Nguyen, 2020). Besides, tourists' satisfaction mediates the destination choice, the decision of consuming tourism products and services, and tourists' intention to revisit (Kozak & Rimmington, 2000). Surprisingly, no universal set of standard attributes has been developed to measure tourist satisfaction across diverse destinations (Dwyer, Cvelbar, Mihalič, & Koman, 2014). Furthermore, as part of destination image, transportation facilities might positively enhance tourists' satisfaction, and influence revisit intentions (Islam, Hossain, & Noor, 2017).

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Even though tourist spots' readiness is notably associated with tourists' revisit intentions, previous tourism research on this relationship is scant, especially in developing and least developed countries (LDCs). As destination competitiveness attributes are location-specific (Dwyer et al., 2014), previous research of similar scope in developed countries might not be appropriate in designing tourism policies and services for other developing and LDCs. Tourism has a greater association with economic development and growth, which could benefit residents of LDCs with economic diversification and skills development (Saner, Yiu, & Filadoro, 2019). Besides, authors also contend that LDCs can offer a very different tourism experience to domestic and international tourists by offering their different unexploited environmental and cultural assets. Previous literature supports that tourist spots' readiness not only directly influences tourists' decision of revisiting the spot but also generates tourists' satisfaction, and such satisfaction again influences tourists to revisit the same destination (Markus, Perovic, Pekovic, & Popovic, 2019; Zhang, Wu, & Buhalis, 2018). However, this mediating role of tourists' satisfaction in the relationship between tourist spots' readiness and tourists' revisit intentions and the moderating role of transportation facilities in the relationship between tourists' satisfaction and revisit intention in LDCs are not adequately researched previously.

To minimize this gap, this study explores the effect of tourist spots' readiness on tourists' revisit intention in a selected LDC and considers Bangladesh as representative. Bangladesh embraces outstanding opportunities in tourism with its forests, hills, valleys, sea, beaches, and broad rivers (Hossain & Islam, 2019). The country is blessed with two world heritage sites, the Sundarbans, the world's largest natural mangrove forest, and Cox's Bazar sea beach, the world's longest unbroken sea beach (Islam et al., 2017). These natural resources and other tourism amenities attract millions of domestic and foreign tourists to the country's different tourist spots all-round the year. In 2019, domestic visitors spent around USD 8,038.3 million (96% of the total), and foreign visitors spent USD 354.5 million (4% of the total) (World Travel & Tourism Council, 2021). The industry contributed 2.7% of the national gross domestic product (GDP) and 1.86 million employees. This scenario indicates considerable potential for tourism in Bangladesh, where policymakers and practitioners require further insights.

This study addresses five research objectives, of which three (i, ii and iii) explore the direct relationship among study variables, and two (iv and v) are relevant for a better understanding of mediating role and moderating role of study variables:

- i) To identify the effect of readiness of tourist spots on tourists' revisit intention
- ii) To examine the impact of readiness of tourist spots on tourists' satisfaction
- iii) To evaluate the effect of tourists' satisfaction on tourists' revisit intention
- iv) To assess the mediating effect of tourists' satisfaction on the relationship between the readiness of tourist spots and tourists' revisit intention
- v) To observe the moderating effect of transportation facilities on the relationship between the tourists' satisfaction and revisit intention

This study makes three main contributions. First, this study improves the current literature on tourist spots' readiness, tourists' revisit intention, tourists' satisfaction, and transportation facilities, enhancing the scope of further research in these fields. Second, the policymakers get new insights about Bangladeshi tourist spots' readiness, tourists' satisfaction, transportation facilities, and tourists' revisit intention. Policy measures are expected to facilitate more infrastructure, especially in transportation and communication, improve destination image, and increase destination competitiveness. Finally, this study outlines the role of tourists' satisfaction and transportation facilities in bringing the tourists repeatedly to the same spot, which would be an essential consideration for destination managers. Destination managers will understand how to design services and facilities to bring the same tourists and ensure a positive word of mouth and recommendation from the current visitors to the potential future ones.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the research framework and the development of hypotheses. The methodology of the study is described in Section 3. Section 4 presents the results and relevant discussion. Finally, Section 6 concludes the study.

2. RESEARCH FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

This study deals with four different variables: tourist spots' readiness is the independent variable, tourists' revisit intention is the dependent variable, tourists' satisfaction is the mediating variable, and transportation facilities is the moderating variable. The research framework is developed based on the existing literature of these four variables, depicted in Figure 1. This framework and proposed hypotheses are discussed in detail in the following.

Source : Authors' development based on previous literature

Figure 1: Research Framework of the Study

2.1 Tourist Spots' Readiness and Tourists' Revisit Intention

Tourist spots' readiness and tourists' revisit intention received much attention individually in tourism research over the last few decades. Different destination attributes create a favorable overall image of the destination, positively influencing the tourists' experience and visit intention (Phau, Quintal, & Shanka, 2014). Destination image also affects tourists' evaluation of different experiences and behavior (Herrero, San Martin, Salmones, & Collado, 2017). Therefore, the readiness of a tourist spot affects tourists' attitude toward a place or attracts tourists to visit and motivates revisit of the place (Huang & Hsu, 2009; Phillips, Asperin, & Wolfe, 2013). Nguyen (2020) proposed a positive influence of destination image on tourists' attitudes toward a future revisit. Rajesh (2013) modeled destination image as a construct that creates tourists' loyalty toward a place, expressed in revisit, word of mouth, and recommendations to others. Therefore, this study hypothesized that,

H₁ : There is a positive effect of tourist spot' readiness on tourists' revisit intention

2.2 Tourist Spots' Readiness and Tourists' Satisfaction

Previous researchers considered destination image and destination competitiveness framework to determine the readiness of a tourist spot in attracting tourists. If a destination has a positive image in tourists' perception, it is more likely to attract more tourists and increase tourists' satisfaction (Islam & Khayer, 2018; Zhang et al., 2018). Researchers also argue that the presence of required destination attributes not only adequately attract tourists toward a destination but also generate expected profits for managers and make the place competitive (Dwyer et al., 2014; Zehrer, Smeral, & Hallmann, 2017). Different destination attributes positively influence the tourists' experience and generate satisfaction (Correia, Kozak, & Ferradeira, 2013; Islam & Khayer, 2018). Therefore, this study hypothesized that,

H₂ : There is a positive effect of tourist spots' readiness on tourists' satisfaction

2.3 Tourists' Satisfaction and Tourists' Revisit Intention

Tourists with a positive experience and satisfaction level are more likely to revisit the same spot or recommend others, which results in higher economic returns for the destination (Correia et al., 2013). Tourists' revisit intention is also considered an extension of the tourists' satisfaction (Um, Chon, & Ro, 2006). When tourists are satisfied with tourism products, services, or other resources, they become interested in revisiting, recommending others, and positively contributing to the destination image (Nguyen, 2020). Several researchers proposed that tourists' satisfaction positively influences tourists' loyalty, which influences the revisit decision of the tourists (Li, Lien, Wang, Wang, & Dong, 2020; Nguyen, 2020). Therefore, this study hypothesized that,

H₃ : There is a positive effect of tourists' satisfaction on tourists' revisit intention

Previous literature also suggests that tourists' satisfaction connects both tourist spots' readiness and tourists' revisit intention. The tourist spots' readiness favorably influences tourists' satisfaction, resulting in tourists' loyalty and motivation to revisit the same place (Nguyen, 2020). It can be assumed that tourists' satisfaction performs the mediating role between the readiness of tourist spots and tourists' revisit intention. Destination attributes related to transportation and communication can also influence tourists' revisit intention even when they are satisfied with the tourism experience. Transportation facilities like availability and quality of transportation services, easy access, and quality of tourism infrastructure, roads, and highways importantly shape destination competitiveness and tourists' satisfaction which might further influence tourists' revisit decisions (Islam et al., 2017; Islam & Khayer, 2018). Therefore, it can be assumed that transportation facilities moderate the tourists' satisfaction and revisit intention. Therefore, this study hypothesized that,

H₄ : There is a positive mediating effect of tourists' satisfaction on the relationship between the readiness of tourist spots and tourists' revisit intention

H₅ : There is a moderating effect of transportation facilities on the relationship between the tourists' satisfaction and revisiting intention

3. METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a quantitative research approach, which investigates the propositions by analyzing the prevailing relationship among measured variables through statistical procedures (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). People who have visited at least once within two years- February 2018 to February 2020 have been considered for this study. Since the population is unknown, a sample of slightly more than 380 is representative (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970). However, this study considers a sample of fifty respondents from each of the eight divisions of Bangladesh, constituting a sample of a total of 400 tourists. Purposive sampling, a non-probability sampling technique, is employed to collect data from respondents. A structured survey questionnaire is distributed online from September 2020 to February 2021. Among the distributed questionnaires of 400, 358 replies were received, yielding an 89.5 percent response rate, which is adequate to apply the PLS-path model (Fan, Mahmood, & Uddin, 2019). However, another 52 questionnaires were found incomplete. Thus, the final sample size is 306.

Table 1 : Demographic Profile of Respondents

Particulars	Percentage
Gender	
Male	80.72%
Female	19.28%
Age	
11 to 20	10.78%

21 to 30	55.23%
31 to 40	20.59%
41 to 50	8.50%
50+	4.90%
Educational Qualification	
SSC	5.23%
HSC	20.59%
Bachelors/Honors	32.68%
Masters	33.00%
Others	8.50%
Average length of stay during a visit	
≤ 4 days	76.47 %
≥ 5 days	23.53%
Number of travels last 3 years	
≤ 3 times	67.65%
≥ 4 times	32.35%
Sources of Information for choosing the place	
Friends/relatives/business associates	64.25%
Media (Travel booklet, TV, Radio, Internet)	22.47%
Travel agencies	7.00%
National tourist organizations	6.28%

Source : Primary data collection, 2021

The survey questionnaire used in data collection consists of two main sections. Section 'A' comprised questions related to tourists' demographic profiles, and section 'B' comprised questions related to study variables. Table 1 shows the demographic features of the respondents. Around 80% of the respondents are male, while the rest are female. The highest percentage of the respondents belongs to the age group of 21-30 years, followed by 31-40 years. Nearly two-thirds of the respondents hold a bachelor's or master's degree, while the rest have an education qualification of SSC or HSC. Nearly 75% of the respondents stayed a maximum of four days in a place while the rest continued for five or more days. More than two-thirds of the respondents visited places three times or more in the previous three years, and the rest visited four times or more in the same period. Finally, two-thirds of the respondents mention that recommendations from friends, relatives, or business associates are the primary source of information while deciding a tourist spot for a visit, followed by media.

Table 2 : Measures adapted in this Study

Construct	No of Items	Example Items	Sources
Readiness of Tourist Spots	6	Reasonable accommodation, quality and variety of food taste and beverage, safety and security	Crouch (2011), Dwyer et al. (2014)
Revisit Intention	5	Intention to revisit within three years, intention to recommend others, friendliness of different tourism services	Nguyen (2020), Zhang et al. (2018)
Tourists' Satisfaction	10	Price of different products, natural attractions, ambiance and amenities, shopping and entertainment	Nguyen (2020), Rajesh (2013)
Transportation Facilities	3	Quality of transportation infrastructure, roads and highways, availability and easy access to transportation services	Islam et al. (2017), Islam and Khayer (2018)

Source : Authors' development based on previous literature

In addition to the demographic profile, the survey questionnaire includes the measurement of selected four study variables. Each variable employed several items where the responses to items were rated on a 5-point scale ranging from strongly agree (5) to strongly disagree (1). The items are selected based on previous research in the tourism field. The three variables- readiness of tourist spots, revisit intention and tourists' satisfaction and their associated items are selected from previous studies in other country settings, which considered the direct and mediating relationships stated in this study. Besides, transportation facilities and its associated items are selected from previous tourism studies focused in Bangladesh. The details of the variables with the sources from which items are adapted are shown in Table 2.

In the analysis of the relationship among variables, the PLS-SEM is used with the help of Smart PLS version 3. PLS-SEM assesses the mediating effect of tourists' satisfaction in the relationship between tourist spots' readiness and revisit intention and moderating effect of transportation facilities between tourists' satisfaction and revisit intention. The PLS-SEM is a variance-based estimation process that assesses the constructs' reliability and validity and estimates the relationships between those variables (Barroso, Carrión, & Roldán, 2010). Consequently, the data analysis method used in this research contains two sub-processes. First, to assess the measurement model in order to ensure the reliability and validity of each indicator. Second, to evaluate the structural model through the examination of the coefficient

of determination (R^2), predictive relevance (Q^2), effect size (f^2), and goodness of fit model, as well as testing of both direct and indirect hypotheses using a 95% confidence interval.

4. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

This study predicts the relationships among the study variables using Smart PLS-SEM, where the first phase is the assessment of the measurement model (outer model), and the second phase is the assessment of the structural model (inner model) (Hair, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2011). The inner model determines the relationship between exogenous and endogenous variables, while the outer model determines the relationship between constructs and related indicators (Hair, Sarstedt, Hopkins, & Kuppelwieser, 2014).

4.1 Common Method Bias

Before assessing both measurement and structural models, this study applied Harman's single-factor test to check the common method variance (CMV) in the data. Uddin, Mahmood and Fan (2019) suggested that if a single factor explains more than 50% of the total variation, considerable bias in the sample is possible. Thus, this study has no CMV problems, as a single factor may explain only 39.83 percent of the overall variance.

4.2 Assessment of Measurement Model

The assessment of the measurement model is required for reliability and validity, where internal consistency, convergent validity, and discriminant validity are usually tested (Hair et al., 2014). The internal consistency reflects the model reliability, whereas convergent and discriminant validity reflects model validity. The reliability of the proposed model has been determined based on the Cronbach alpha and composite reliability (CR), where a model is considered reliable if CR exceeds 0.70 (Hair, Anderson, Babin, & Black, 2010) and the alpha value is more than 0.70 (Robinson, Shaver, & Wrightsman, 1991). Nunnally (1978) further supports that an alpha value between 0.50 and 0.60 is acceptable in the early stages of model development. Table 3 demonstrates that all Cronbach alpha and CR exceeded the recommended value of 0.70, confirming the reliability of the model, items, and constructs. Further, both convergent validity and discriminant validity are assessed to establish the model's validity. The average variance extracted (AVE) is used to assess the measurement model's convergent validity, where the suggested value of AVE is greater than 0.5 (Hair, Hult, Ringle, Sarstedt, & Thiele, 2017). Table 3 presents that the AVE score for all constructs exceeds the minimum acceptable value of 0.50, providing adequate support to the convergent validity.

Table 3 : Evaluation of the Measurement Model

Construct/Items	Factor Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE
Tourist Spots' Readiness		0.968	0.974	0.861
TSR 1	0.938			
TSR 2	0.939			
TSR 3	0.946			
TSR 4	0.908			
TSR 5	0.928			
TSR 6	0.907			
Revisit Intention		0.858	0.898	0.637
RI1	0.839			
RI2	0.826			
RI3	0.776			
RI4	0.776			
RI5	0.772			
Tourists' Satisfaction		0.951	0.962	0.763
TS1	0.529			
TS2	0.920			
TS3	0.902			
TS4	0.920			
TS6	0.859			
TS7	0.926			
TS9	0.927			
TS10	0.928			
Transportation Facilities		0.759	0.862	0.675
TF1	0.804			
TF2	0.864			
TF3	0.796			

Source : Primary data collection, 2021 [Note: TSR = Tourist Spots' Readiness, RI = Revisit Intention, TS = Tourists' Satisfaction, TF = Transportation Facilities; Items TS5 and TS8 is deleted]

In the assessment of discriminant validity, Fornell and Larcker criterion and HTMT criterion have been used. According to Fornell and Larcker (1981) and Hair et al. (2010), the AVE of the latent variable should be higher than the squared correlation between the latent variable and all other variables. In addition, the HTMT value should be lower than 0.85 to prove discriminant validity (Henseler, Ringle, &

Sarstedt, 2015). Tables 4 and 5 demonstrate the model's discriminant validity by the Fornell and Larcker criterion and the HTMT criterion.

Table 4 : Fornell and Larcker Criterion for Discriminant Validity

Constructs	TSR	RI	TS	TF
Readiness of Tourist Spot	0.928			
Revisit Intention	0.300	0.798		
Tourists' Satisfaction	0.432	0.446	0.873	
Transportation Facilities	0.261	0.468	0.295	0.822

Source: Primary data collection, 2021 [Note: TSR = Tourist Spots' Readiness, RI = Revisit Intention, TS = Tourists' Satisfaction, TF = Transportation Facilities]

Table 5 : Heterotrait Monotrait (HTMT) Criterion for Discriminant Validity

Constructs	TSR	RI	TS	TF
Readiness of Tourist Spot				
Revisit Intention	0.320			
Tourists' Satisfaction	0.443	0.486		
Transportation Facilities	0.302	0.576	0.340	

Source: Primary data collection, 2021 [Note: TSR = Tourist Spots' Readiness, RI = Revisit Intention, TS = Tourists' Satisfaction, TF = Transportation Facilities]

4.3 Assessment of Structural Model

The successful assessment of the measurement model leads to the assessment of the structural model of this study. Researchers need to evaluate the significance of the path coefficient, consider variance explanation of endogenous constructs (R^2), determine effect size (f^2) and predictive relevance (Q^2) to assess the structural model (Henseler, Ringle, & Sinkovics, 2009). Hence, this study considers R^2 , f^2 , Q^2 , Inner Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) (Collinearity testing), and Standardized Root Mean Residual (SRMR) to assess the structural model.

Table 6 : Quality Indices of Structure Model

Constructs	R^2	Inner VIF	f^2	Q^2	SRMR
Readiness of Tourist Spots		1.276	(RI- 0.004; TS-0.229)		0.080
Tourists' Satisfaction		1.130	0.075	0.134	
Transportation Facilities		1.409	0.184		
Tourists' Revisit Intention	0.347			0.210	

Source: Primary data collection, 2021

Table 6 shows the different quality indices of the structural model. Hair et al. (2014) suggested any R^2 greater than 0.20 in behavioral science is acceptable, while Cohen

(2013) suggested an R^2 value of 0.30. In this study, the R^2 value is 0.347 suggests that the model variables can explain 34.7% of the variance of the dependent variable, supporting the significant predictive power of the model. Cohen (2013) described f^2 value of 0.02 as small, 0.15 as moderate, and 0.35 as strong. In this study, the f^2 for tourist spots' readiness to revisit intention is 0.004 revealing no effect. The f^2 for tourist spots' readiness to tourist satisfaction is 0.229, revealing a moderate to strong effect. The f^2 for transportation facilities and tourist satisfaction to revisit intention is 0.184 and 0.075, respectively, revealing medium and small effects. The inner VIF score ranges from 1.276 to 1.409, supporting that the result has no multicollinearity issues. Besides, any SRMR score beneath 0.080 (Hair et al., 2017) and Q^2 value above zero are desirable (Chin, 1998; Henseler et al., 2009). Table 6 reports an SRMR value of 0.080 and Q^2 value of 0.134 for tourist satisfaction and 0.210 for revisit intention, indicating the model's sufficient predictive relevance.

4.4 Test of Direct, Mediating, and Moderating Effects

Under the structural equation modeling, all kinds of effects are studied to test the hypotheses. Hypotheses are confirmed by path coefficient, t statistics, and P value. Table 7 and Figure 2 show all the direct, mediating, and moderating hypotheses. Among the three direct hypotheses, H_2 and H_3 are accepted as with $P < 0.01$ and $t > 1.96$, while H_1 is rejected ($\beta = 0.056$, $t = 1.083 > 1.96$, $P = 0.279 > 0.05$).

This study used PLS bootstrapping to observe the mediation effect of tourists' satisfaction, particularly carried out at 5000 re-samplings to examine the t value. Results from table 7 confirm that tourists' satisfaction mediates the relationship between tourist spots' readiness and tourists' revisit intentions ($\beta = 0.113$, $t = 3.939$ or $P < 0.05$). Moreover, Nitzl, Roldán Salgueiro and Cepeda-Carrión (2016) alluded that a full mediation occurs when the indirect effect is significant, but the direct effect is insignificant. Table 7 and Figure 2 report that both the direct relationships between the readiness of tourist spots and tourists' satisfaction, and tourists' satisfaction and revisit intentions are significant. However, the direct relationship between the readiness of tourist spots and revisit intention is not significant. Thus, H_4 is accepted or shows full mediation.

Table 7 : Test Statistics of Direct, Mediating, and Moderating Effects

HYPOS	Path Relations	β	Mean	SD	t Value	P value	Decision
H_1	TSR -> RI	0.056	0.055	0.052	1.083	0.279	Not Supported
H_2	TSR -> TS	0.432	0.433	0.043	10.084	0.000	Supported
H_3	TS -> RI	0.262	0.259	0.062	4.200	0.000	Supported
H_4	TSR -> TS -> RI	0.113	0.113	0.029	3.939	0.000	Supported
H_5	TS * TF -> RI	0.133	0.141	0.047	2.816	0.005	Supported

Source: Primary data collection, 2021 [Note: TSR = Tourist Spots' Readiness, RI = Revisit Intention, TS = Tourists' Satisfaction, TF = Transportation Facilities; R Square = 0.341]

Source : Primary data collection, 2021

Figure 2 : The Structural Model with Path Estimates

Furthermore, H_5 anticipated that transportation facilities moderate the relationship between tourists' satisfaction and revisit intention. Table 7 and Figure 2 reflect the significant moderating effect of transportation facilities in the relationship between tourists' satisfaction and revisit intention ($\beta = 0.369$, $P = 0.00$). However, Baron and Kenny (1986) suggested that the moderation hypothesis is confirmed if the product term of the predictor and moderator (interaction term) is significant. In this study, the interaction term (tourist satisfaction* transportation facilities) generates a significant result ($\beta = 0.133^*$, $P < 0.05$, $t = 2.816 > 1.96$). Thus, H_5 is confirmed, indicating that transportation facilities significantly strengthen the positive relationship between tourists' satisfaction and revisit intention.

4.5 Discussion

This study finds no direct effect of tourist spots' readiness on tourists' revisit intention, contradicting previous research (Nguyen, 2020; Phillips et al., 2013). The relationship with a t value of 1.083 and β value of 0.056 indicates no substantial effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable. So, there is insufficient statistical evidence to support the hypothesis that tourist spots' readiness positively affects tourists' revisit intention in Bangladesh. In the developed and developing countries, previous studies found that tourist spots' readiness or destination image positively influences tourists' loyalty, resulting in revisiting, word of mouth, and recommendations to others (Nguyen, 2020; Phillips et al., 2013). However, in the context of LDCs, this study contends that tourists consider other influencing and contributing factors in revisiting a place rather than solely considering its image or readiness.

In contrast, this study finds a statistically significant direct positive relationship between tourist spots' readiness and tourists' satisfaction with a t value of 10.084 and a β value of 0.432. The result also matches some of the previous studies, where researchers established a positive association between tourist spots' readiness and tourists' satisfaction (Islam & Khayer, 2018; Zhang et al., 2018). This study also finds a statistically significant direct positive relationship between tourists'

satisfaction and revisit intention with a t value of 4.200 and a β value of 0.262. This finding matches with the findings of some of the previous research, which considers a positive influence of tourists' satisfaction on tourists' loyalty, revisit intention, and recommendation to others (Li et al., 2020; Markus et al., 2019; Nguyen, 2020).

Additionally, this study shows that tourists' satisfaction mediates the relationship between tourist spots' readiness and tourists' revisit intention with a t value of 3.939 and the β value of 0.113. This finding supports a few previous research (Nguyen, 2020; Rajesh, 2013). This study also shows that transportation facilities significantly moderate the relationship between tourists' satisfaction and revisit intention with a t value of 2.816 and a β value of 0.133.

5. CONCLUSION

Destination managers are interested in determining tourists' revisit intentions as repeat visitors generate more revenues for the firms and recommend others. Tourism researchers and policymakers are also concerned with destination image and tourists' satisfaction as it positively contributes to destination competitiveness. Therefore, understanding the relationship between tourist spots' readiness and tourists' revisit intention becomes worthwhile. Previous studies on the effect of tourist spots' readiness on revisit intention are insufficient, especially in LDCs like Bangladesh. Hence, this study determines the effect of Bangladeshi tourist spots' readiness on tourists' revisit intention. This study also considers the mediating role of tourists' satisfaction on the relationship between tourist spots' readiness and tourists' revisit intention and moderating role of transportation facilities on the relationship between tourists' satisfaction and revisit intention.

The findings show no statistically significant effect of tourist spots' readiness on the tourists' revisit intention in Bangladesh. Tourists in Bangladesh perceive a constant image of different spots' readiness while connecting other factors in their revisit decision. This nature of decision-making makes sense when other findings of this study are considered. A direct positive relationship is evident between tourist spots' readiness and tourists' satisfaction and between tourists' satisfaction and revisit intention. The tourist spots' readiness largely shapes tourists' satisfaction, which is more likely to influence tourists to revisit the same destination. Therefore, tourists' satisfaction significantly mediates the relationship between tourist spots' readiness and revisit intention. Additionally, transportation facilities are found significant in moderating the relationship between tourists' satisfaction and revisit intention. Tourists, highly satisfied in their first visit, are likely to revisit when better transportation facilities are offered.

This study creates important implications for academics, policymakers, and tourism practitioners. Considering the importance of tourists' satisfaction and transportation facilities in the relationship between the tourist spots' readiness and revisit intention, destination managers and policymakers should design the tourism facilities for

all intended visitors. A holistic approach including all stakeholders of Bangladesh tourism could be a starting point to design tourism facilities that create a competitive destination image, generate higher satisfaction to visitors, and influence tourists' revisit intention. Additionally, this study broadens the scope of future research in the tourism field. Similar studies might be initiated to examine the relationship between tourist spots' readiness and tourists' revisit intention in specific tourism fields like nature, leisure, medical, education, sports, and in other LDC settings as destination attributes vary among countries (Dwyer et al., 2014). Future studies might also consider this model in examining revisit intention in the specific tourist zone of Bangladesh.

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